

Dr. R.K.B. Law College

Newsletter

Volume 1 Issue 1
(January – June 2023)

Editor: Mr. Jayanta Boruah

From the Principal Desk Editorial

"Legal Literacy is the sine qua non for a developed society. It makes the members of the society aware about their rights and entitlements, encourages to voice against superstitions and inequalities, exploitation and violations going on in the society and thus to live a dignified life."

It is a matter of great honour for me to write this message for the 1st chapter of Dr. R. K. B. Law College News Letter in the history of Dr. R. K. B. Law College. This newsletter is a reflection of multidimensional activities of the members of Dr. R. K. B. Law College. The newsletter reflects our efforts to maintain the wheel of excellence on track. Publication of such a newsletter has been a long standing dream of RKB family. Now as the dream has actually become true, I would like to extend my heartfelt congratulation to Mr. Jayanta Boruah, Editor of this Newsletter and other staff who are associated with this excellent work. I hope this will be a never ending journey of our college.

**Dr. Gautomi Dutta Borah
Principal**

*From the Desk of IQAC
Coordinator*

Dear Readers,

It gives me immense pleasure to connect with you through this edition of our college magazine. As the coordinator of the Internal Quality Assurance Cell (IQAC), I am privileged to witness the growth and development of our institution in various aspects of academic excellence. The IQAC plays a pivotal role in ensuring quality sustenance and enhancement in all dimensions of our college. It continuously strives to improve the teaching- learning process, enhance research and innovation, promote student support services, and foster community engagement. Our constant efforts in aligning with the standards set by accreditation bodies have enabled us to consistently deliver a holistic educational experience to our students. This edition of the magazine serves as a testament to the accomplishment, milestones and success stories of our college community. It reflects the dedication and hard work of our students, faculty and staff members.

I extend my heartfelt appreciation to the editor, contributors and everyone involved in bringing this magazine to life. I encourage all readers to immerse themselves in the diverse range of content present here and be motivated by the achievements of our college.

"Let us together embrace the spirit of quality education and make RKB a beacon of knowledge and transformation"

**Mrs. Shilpi Gupta
IQAC Coordinator**

With great pride and pleasure, we present to you the first issue of our academic newsletter, which highlights the outstanding accomplishments, thought-provoking activities, and academic advancement of our prestigious institution from January to June 2023.

At Dr. R.K.B. Law College, we believe in holistic development. We take immense pride in our students' achievements both inside and outside the classroom - from winning sports competitions to volunteering for social causes. This section showcases the diverse talents and altruistic endeavors of our extraordinary students.

Dr. Rohini Kanta Barua Law College has always stood strong in its quest of excellence in legal education as the preeminent legal institution in the area. Our college serves as a platform for developing future leaders of the legal fraternity as well as a hub for the exchange of ideas, a furnace for encouraging intellectual curiosity, and a venue for knowledge dissemination.

We present to you a wealth of interesting experiences in this issue, emphasizing the devotion and dedication of our students, instructors, and staff in reaching outstanding milestones. We are excited to highlight some of the most noteworthy experiences and triumphs that have contributed to the past six months being a truly extraordinary trip.

The Dr. R.K.B. Law College Newsletter is a window into the dynamic and vibrant life of our institution. We extend our heartfelt gratitude to all contributors and the editorial team for their dedicated efforts in bringing this vision to life.

As we forge ahead, we envision this newsletter becoming a vital platform for engagement, inspiration, and unity within our college community. Together, let us continue to empower minds and enrich futures, creating a brighter tomorrow for ourselves and the world of law.

**Mr. Jayanta Boruah
Editor**

Major Headings at a Glance

- Saraswati Puja Celebration
- Annual College Week
- 2nd Edition of N. C. Gohain Memorial Wall Magazine Competition
- Observation of World Consumer Rights Day
- 2 Days International Seminar on Responsibilities of Industrial Corporations in Achieving Sustainable Development in the Present Ecologically Critical Period
- Bihu Celebration with Great Enthusiasm and Delight
- Observation of World Earth Day
- World Red Cross Day Observation
- Intra-College Moot Court Competition 2023
- Observation of World Environment Day
- Victory at P. Khaitan Memorial Moot Court Competition in Tinsukia Law College
- Research Activities of Dr. R.K.B. Law College
- Beginning of 5 Years BBA,LL.B Course
- Policies of Good Practices

About the Institution

The Dr. Rohini Kanta Barua Law College, formerly known as Dibrugarh Law College, is an educational institution that was established in 1976 in Dibrugarh, Assam, India. It was the outcome of a public meeting of citizens of Dibrugarh held on 20th June 1976, with Shri Pramode Kumar Das, B.L., as the chairperson. The primary objective of the college was to provide legal education to the people of Dibrugarh and create a new avenue for students interested in the legal field.

The college is located in the heart of Dibrugarh town and is permanently affiliated with Dibrugarh University. It has received approval from the Bar Council of India, New Delhi, which is the regulatory body for legal education in India.

On 4th February 1994, the college was renamed as 'Dr. Rohini Kanta Barua Law College' to honor the memory of Dr. Rohini Kanta Barua, a renowned figure in scientific research and academic excellence. This renaming was made possible by the generous contribution of late Muktalata Barua, the wife of Dr. Rohini Kanta Barua, who donated the land and building (present administrative wing) to the college.

Since its renaming, the Dr. Rohini Kanta Barua Law College has made significant progress and development in terms of facilities for students, meeting the requirements set by the Bar Council of India. The college provides a rich environment for studying law and aims to prepare students for a successful entry into the legal profession. Over the years, the college has consistently achieved good results in the LL.B Examinations conducted by Dibrugarh University. Many of its alumni have gone on to excel in various legal professions, such as practicing law in different Bars of the state, serving in the Judiciary, and succeeding in other fields as well. Overall, the Dr. R.K.B. Law College has played a vital role in imparting legal education and contributing to the legal community and society as a whole. Recently, the institution has received approval for 5 year BBA.LL.B course from BCI and Dibrugarh University.

Dr. Rohini Kanta Barua Law College

Glimpses

Saraswati Puja Celebration

January 26, 2023: Dr. R.K.B. Law College began the new academic year with the celebration of Saraswati Puja with full devotion for the blessings of Maa Saraswati. The puja was organized with great devotion and according to the Hindu and local customary rituals. Prayer was offered and at the end of puja Prasad distribution was done. Many students and faculties prayed before Maa Saraswati to

get enlightened with the knowledge and intellectualities. This puja is celebrated to rescue us from the darkness of ignorance and to inculcate true values of knowledge. Being an educational institution, observation of such rituals demonstrates the spiritual and cultural values that enable us to preserve our identity and humbleness in the modern world.

Annual College Week

February 22, 2023: The annual college week of Dr. R.K.B. Law College was held from 22nd to 25th February, 2023 to allow the students to demonstrate and express their extracurricular talents and skills. This event was also special because after a long period of shut down due to corona pandemic, it was again resumed. The students were found to be much delighted and their participation was highly active. The event started with the flag hoisting ceremony followed by cultural rally.

Subsequently, a number of competitions were held under different categories, namely Outdoor sports, Indoor Sports, Literature and Cultural events. The Outdoor sports category, included Tug of War, Kabadi, Running Race, Cricket (Female), Discus Throw, Shot Put, and Go as you like; the Indoor Sports category included Carom, Badminton, Rangoli,

Salad Decoration Competition; Literature category included Debate, Quiz, Extempore Speech, Poem Recitation, Book Review, and Traditional Dress Code Competition; and the Cultural events category included Cultural Rally, Singing, Dancing, Chorus, Biya Naam, and Drama competitions. Overall the entire events ended with great success.

Painting/Drawing, Arm Wrestling, Chess, Mehendi Competition, Hair Dressing Competi-

2nd Edition of N. C. Gohain Memorial Wall Magazine Competition

February 25, 2023: The Students' Development Committee of Dr. Rohini Kanta Barua Law College, Dibrugarh organized the second episode of N.C. Gohain Memorial Wall Magazine Competition among students of 2nd, 4th & 6th Semesters on the theme of Nature vs. Nurture. The students are supervised by Ms. Manalisa Medhi (2nd Semester), Ms. Ritimoni Sarma (4th Semester), and Dr. Manomita Paul (6th Semester). The Wall Magazines were inaugurated on 25th February 2023. The Inaugural programme got started with a welcome note delivered by Dr. G. D. Borah, Principal of Dr. R.K.B. Law College. Thereafter students felicitated the distinguished judges Dr. Rupam Saikia, Inspector of Colleges, Dibrugarh University, and Dr. Mahesh Kumar Jain, Former Vice Principal, Dibru College, Dibrugarh with

Phoolam Gamuchas. The two distinguished judges illuminated the necessity and importance of Wall magazine in a College for enhancing various qualities of students by promoting creativity, teamwork, awareness on social issues, etc.

Thereafter, the judges inaugurated the wall magazines of all three semesters. On assessment by the Judges, the 2nd Semester won 1st Prize, 4th Semester and 6th Semester won 2nd prize.

All were congratulated for the successful completion of the event and the prizes of the Wall magazine competition was distributed in the event of the college week prize distribution ceremony on the same day. With this event both the events of the College Week and the Wall Magazine Competitions were concluded.

Observation of World Consumer Rights Day

March 15, 2023: The Nyaya Sarathi (Legal Advice Cell) of Dr. R.K.B Law College, Dibrugarh, Assam in association with IQAC, NLB City College, Dibrugarh, Assam observed World Consumer Rights Day in the Conference Hall of NLB City College. The event proceeded with the welcome speech from the Principal of NLB City College, Sanjeevananda Borgohain at around 11:30 AM in the presence of the Vice Principal, Dr. Manashi Gogoi, and other faculty members of City College and Dr. R.K.B Law College and students from both the institu-

tions. The event was moderated by Mrs. Monalisa Medhi, Assistant Professor of Dr. R.K.B. Law College, and was attended by around 50 students. The welcome speech was followed by a speech delivered by the Keynote speaker, Mr. Jayanta Boruah, Assistant Professor of Dr. R.K.B. Law College on the topic of Rights, Remedies, and Responsibilities of the Consumers in India through PowerPoint presentation. The speech was followed by three advertisement demonstrations performed by Ritishna Chetry, Bedanta Choudhury, and Manisha Thapa respectively that included two misleading advertisements and one genuine advertisement. The audience was suggested to prefer one item and a majority of the audience was found to have been influenced by the misleading advertise-

ments. The event was moderated by Mrs. Monalisa Medhi, Assistant Professor of Dr. R.K.B. Law College, and was attended by around 50 students. The welcome speech was followed by a speech delivered by the Keynote speaker, Mr. Jayanta Boruah, Assistant Professor of Dr. R.K.B. Law College on the topic of Rights, Remedies, and Responsibilities of the Consumers in India through PowerPoint presentation. The speech was followed by three advertisement demonstrations performed by Ritishna Chetry, Bedanta Choudhury, and Manisha Thapa respectively that included two misleading advertisements and one genuine advertisement. The audience was suggested to prefer one item and a majority of the audience was found to have been influenced by the misleading advertise-

2 Days International Seminar on Responsibilities of Industrial Corporations in Achieving Sustainable Development in the Present Ecologically Critical Period

March 17, 2023: Dr. Rohini Kanta Barua Law College of Dibrugarh and Nowgong Law College of Nagaon in their joint venture in pursuit of academic excellence have organized an International Seminar with the sponsorship of OIL, Duliajan on "Responsibilities of Industrial Corporations in Achieving Sustainable Development in the Present Ecologically Critical Period" on 17th and 18th March 2023. The seminar was graced by Prof. Abani Bhagwati, Professor of Geography (Retd.) Gauhati University, Prof. Tara Prasad Sapkota, Retd. Prof. Trivuban University, Nepal, Prof. Dr.Tushar Kanti Saha, Dr. R.K.B. Law College

Retd. Vice Chancellor, Starford International University, South Sudan, Prof. S. Rajkhowa, Professor, USTM and Former Dean Dept. of Law, Gauhati University, and Dr. Rupam Saikia, Inspector of Colleges, Dibrugarh University. More than 100 participants were present in the seminar and 30 paper presenters from different parts of the world presented papers on different subthemes of the seminar. Thus, Seminar created a platform for discussion on sustainable economic development for the survival of human civilization across the globe. It also stimulated awareness of on sustainable development among the participants vis-à-vis the responsibilities of industrial corporations. Keynote speaker Prof. T.P Sapkota in his speech discussed the misuse and exploitation of Earth's natural resources. He emphasized the fact that sustainable development is not an option rather it is a must for securing the resources for the generations to come.

Prof. S. Rajkhowa urged the participants to behave in a sustainable manner. The generations to come too have a share of what we are enjoying today. However unregulated activities of industries have created a threat to such resources and that instant corrective measures are the need of the hour.

Prof. T. K. Saha in his speech said, "To survive and sustain we must not damage the natural resources. There should be zero tolerance for pollution and steps must be taken to eradicate rather than reduce it. 'Every human comfort is a discomfort to nature' quoting

this Prof Bhagawati, in his inaugural speech drew attention to the inter-link between different disciplines and proposed four mega processes i.e., agricultural modernization, industrial revolution, urbanization and globalization for enabling sustainable development. He covered some of the important topics like technosphere, increasing population and the problems associated with that.

Dr Gautomi Dutta, Principal, Dr. R.K.B. Law college expressed her gratitude to the dignitaries and spoke about the purpose of organizing the seminar.

Dr. Sujata Bhattacharyya, principal, Nowgong Law College, delivered the Vote of Thanks to all the dignitaries present there.

The seminar was ended with a valedictory session presided over by Mr. Sarat Ch. Khound, Advocate and President, Governing Body, Nowgong Law College, Nagaon, Assam. He also emphasized on the fact that law alone cannot control pollution and public awareness is a must for creating a balance between sustainability and development and to create a better world.

Bihu Celebration with Great Enthusiasm and Delight

April 10, 2023: The students of Dr. R.K.B. Law College observed Rongali Bihu with great enthusiasm and delight. Both the Teaching

and the Non-Teaching Staff participated. Since Bihu is the pride of Assam and Rongali Bihu marks the beginning of Spring festival in the region, the students joined with the administrative staff of the institution and celebrated the festival. Bihu songs were sang and dances were performed. Traditional *jaalpaan* with *seera, doi, gur* and cream was served by the institution to all the members who participated in the event. Two professional singers were also invited to join the event and to make the celebration more enthusiastic with their wonderful performances. The event was anchored by Mr. Jayanta Boruah, Assistant Professor of the institution and was inaugurated

by Dr. Prakash Barua, President of the Governing Body. Other members from the Governing Body were also present as Guest of Honors along with the Principal. Finally, all the faculties, students and the

members from the audience participated and performed the *Bihu Husauri*. At last the event was finally concluded with the alumni enjoying few moments with the present students.

Observation of World Earth Day

April 27, 2023: A wonderful initiative was taken by Dr. R.K.B. Law College to observe World Earth Day. Organizing a procession on environmental awareness is a great way to raise public consciousness about the importance of protecting the environment. Such processions can help educate people about environmental issues and inspire them

to take action. In addition to the procession, planting saplings at DTP Dyke in the district of Dibrugarh is a commendable effort towards environmental conservation. Planting trees is crucial for maintaining a healthy ecosystem, as they contribute to reducing carbon dioxide levels, improving air quality, and providing habitats for various

species. By combining these activities, Dr. R.K.B. Law College demonstrated their commitment to creating awareness about environmental issues and actively contributing to the betterment of the environment. Such initiatives play a vital role in promoting sustainable practices and inspiring others to take similar actions.

World Red Cross Day Observa- tion

May 08, 2023: On the occasion of World Red Cross Day, the Dibrugarh District Branch of the Indian Red Cross Society in association with the Youth Red Cross Unit of Dr. R. K. B. Law College, Dibrugarh celebrated World Red Cross Day with a variety of Programmes at the Auditorium of the college. The event was inaugurated by Dr. Trishna Bora, Joint Director of Health Services, Dibrugarh. The Chairman of IRCS, Dr. Pranit Kumar Chowdhury delivered a welcome speech and briefed the participants on the activities of the branch. The Vice President of IRCS, Dibrugarh Dr. Raghunath Borbora announced the objectives of the meeting. On this occasion, the theme song of the IRCS, written by the writer cum poet Dr. Karabi Deka Hazarika, and composed by Dr. Nirode Baruah, Vice Chancellor of Majuli University of Culture was released and it became the highlight of the Programme. Dr. Bharati Dutta, writer and Life Member explained the importance of the Day and spoke on the philosophy of Sir Dunant, the founder of the Red Cross Society. Dr. Trishna Bora in her speech praised the IRCS's activities and urged each members to continue

working with the motto of the Red Cross Society. She assured to cooperate with society in matters related to health. The event was attended by the social worker Smt. Niharika Chowdhury who in her speech urged everyone to help the poor, lowly and backward people of the society to stand up and lend a helping hand in the time of crisis. The other highlights of the programme included the recitation of a poem by Dr. Sultana Hazarika. Dr. Runuma Sarma, an educationist and social worker anchored the entire Programme. Last but not least, the vote of thanks was provided by renowned Social Worker SmtiNiharika Shrutikar, and at the end, the entire programme was concluded with the state anthem being sung by all the present dignitaries.

Intra-College Moot Court Competition 2023

May 20, 2023: The Moot Court Society of Dr. Rohini Kanta Baruah Law College, Dibrugarh, Assam organized an Intra-College Moot Court Competition on May 20, 2023. The objective of the competition was to inculcate the skills of mooting amongst the college students for preparing a team for inter-college moot competition in the future. The Judges for the competition were Advocate Himanshu Bagaria appointed as an external Judge, Advocate Ajit Bargohain, Advocate R.K. Agarwal, and Mr. Jayanta Boruah (Faculty Coordinator of Moot Court Society) appointed as internal Judges. In total 16 teams participated in the competi-

tion. The event started with a welcome speech by Mr. Jayanta Boruah and felicitation of all the Judges. Akash Kumar Rajak and Afreen Hussain, students of LLB 4th Semester were appointed as Clerks.

The winners of the competition are as follows:
1. Best Moot Team was jointly shared by two teams: The students are Tajmin Sultana, Ridip Dutta and Sonali Kostha and Bijoy Prakash Kujur, Bikash Bhattarai and Jinu Chiangmai;

2. Runners-up Moot Team was again achieved by two teams jointly. The students are: Karishma Das, Angshuman Pareek and Saleha

Rahman and Sobha Pashwam, Binita Chhetri, and Binita Verma;

3. The Best Mooter award was secured by Angshuman Pareek;

4. The Runners-up Mooter was jointly secured by Binita Chhetri and Bikash Bhattarai;

The event was then followed by an award distribution ceremony and remarks from the respective Judges. It was finally concluded with a vote of thanks by Mr. Jayanta Boruah. The event is expected to encourage the students to participate in moot courts in the future.

Observation of World Environment Day

June 5, 2023: The Eco-sense Club of Dr. R.K.B Law College, Dibrugarh, Assam, in association with Pollution Control Board, Assam, Regional Office, Dibrugarh organized a day-long environmental awareness programme on the topic "Solutions to Plastic Pollution". As a part of this programme, an inter-district level art and extempore speech competition were organized among students ranging from standard I to standard 12 and above. The art competition was held in three categories including Category A from Class I to Class V; Category B from Class VI to Class X and Category C from Class XI and above. The extempore speech was held among students from Class xi and above.

The event started with the plantation of saplings jointly by Dr.Gautomi Dutta Borah, Principal Dr. R.K.B Law College and Mr. H. Pegu, Regional Executive Engineer, Regional Office, Dibrugarh. After conducting an inspection of the campus of Dr. R.K.B Law College, the officials of Pollution Control Board declared it as a Plastic Free Campus. Subsequently, the event was followed by the art competition along with the extempore speech competition.

After the competition, a lunch break was provided to all the participants and the audience including the volunteers. It was followed by a keynote session where the resource person was facilitated. Dr.PankajChetia, Associate Professor, Department of Life Science, Dibrugarh University delivered the keynote address as a resource person. Further, Mr. H. Pegu, Dr.GautomiDutta Borah, the Judges of the Art Competition namely Mr.Khargapani Barman and Deba Krishna Boruah, and the Judges of the Extempore Speech Competition namely Dr.BorunDey, Assistant Professor, Department of Political Science, Dibrugarh University and Mr.Jayanta Boruah, Assistant Professor of Law, Dr. R.K.B Law College were also felicitated.

Subsequently, the event was followed by a prize distribution ceremony where the winners of both competitions were provided with their respective prizes. Finally, after the formal vote of thanks provided by Dr.BijetaChetry, Faculty Coordinator of Eco-sense Club, the event was concluded with the singing of the State Anthem.

Tree plantation

The event started with plantation of trees inside the college campus. It was jointly conducted by members of SPCBA Regional Office and the faculty staff and students of Dr. R.K.B Law College.

Declaration of Plastic Free Zone

The campus of Dr. R.K.B. Law College was made plastic free by a massive cleanliness drive and the Principal declared it as a Plastic Free Zone under the Mission Life Campaign launched nationally by Government of India. The declaration for the said cause was read by the Principal in front of the august gathering.

Inter-District Art and Extempore Speech Competition

The inter district art and extempore speech competition on the themes relevant to environment protection was organized subsequently to educate the common public about the need of environment protection and steps to be taken as responsible citizens for a better future.

Victory at P. Khaitan Memorial Moot Court Competition in Tinsukia Law College

June 10, 2023: A Regional Moot Court Competition was organized by Tinsukia Law College under the banner of P. Khaitan Memorial Moot Court Competition between all the colleges affiliated to the Dibrugarh University, Dibrugarh, Assam. Students of Dr. R.K.B. Law College participated in the competition under the guidance of Mr. Jayanta Boruah, Assistant Professor, Dr. R.K.B. Law College. The competition was organized in two phases: Preliminary and the Final Phases. The

students of Dr. R.K.B. Law College first won the preliminary phase against the students of Dibrugarh University and then qualified for the final phase against the students of Tinsukia Law College. Finally R.K.B. Law College won the final phase after a tough competition. The names of the students representing Dr. R.K.B. Law College were Mr. Angshuman Parek, Mr. Bikash Batharai and Mr. Prashanjit Nath. The students demonstrated their excellent skills of advocacy.

Research Activities of Dr. R.K.B. Law College

Dr. R.K.B. Law College has showed its immense interest by engaging in a number of research activities. The main objective behind undertaking such activities is to build an endeavour of research within and outside the campus. The research activities have successfully involved a number of students along with teaching and non-teaching staff of the institution. Serious efforts have been dedicated so far in successfully conducting such activities that are further expected to bring welfare to the society and make valuable contributions to the available piece of literature.

Action Research

In the later half of the year 2022, the Research Committee of Dr. R.K.B. Law College with the assistance from the IQAC decided to conduct an action research on the human rights of forest dwellers across the State of Assam. This research was decided to be jointly conducted in association with the Nowgong Law College, Nagaon, Assam and the Kokrajhar Law College, Kokrajhar, Assam. Mr. Jayanta Boruah, Assistant Professor of Dr. R.K.B. Law College was instructed to take the charge of doing the research in the said direction. A number of virtual sessions by Mr. Boruah were organized with the students of all the above-mentioned three institutions jointly where instructions for data collection were given.

Subsequently, field visits were initiated which got accomplished in the month of March 2023. The preparation of report of the research is underway.

The students of Dr. R.K.B. Law College went to the forest areas of Dibrugarh, Lakhimpur, Dhemaji, Sivasagar, Tinsukia, Jorhat and Golaghat. The students of Nowgong Law College went to the forest areas of Nagaon, Hojai, Morigaon, Karbi-Anglong East, and Karbi-Anglong West. The students of Kokrajhar Law College went to the forest areas of Bajali, Nalbari, Tamulpur, South Salmara Mancachar, etc. And the rest of the districts were surveyed by Mr. Boruah with the help of other supporters from across the State.

Green Audit Report

The institution has also pledged itself to accomplish the task of preparing a Green Audit Report by the end of October 2023. Already the survey of the energy and water intakes has been completed under the supervision of Mr. Jayanta Boruah. Electricity Bills were also collected.

Recently in the month of June, the water sample from the campus of the institution

was also tested in the Public Health Department of the Dibrugarh District. Further, the level of air pollution was also tested by inviting members from the Assam State Pollution Control Board.

The report is expected to help the institution in adopting more efficient steps for ensuring better environmental safety and efficient utilization of the natural resources for day-to-day activities of the institution.

Journal Publication

The institution also has inaugurated a journal in the name of Annual International Journal on Intellectual Property and Corporate Affairs (AIJIPCA) for publishing research works in the field of intellectual property and business law. It is even supported by the Nowgong Law College, Nagaon, Assam and the Aequitas Victoria Foundation.

The journal has received an extensive support and the review process for its first volume has been almost completed.

The first volume of the journal is expected to get published at the end of October this year. The Editor-in-Chief is the famous academician of Assam Prof. (Dr.) Subhram Rajkhowa while the Board of Editors consists of other national and foreign academicians who are experts in the area of the journal. The journal is expected to publish quality research work.

Beginning of 5 Years BBA.LL.B Course

June 15, 2023: Dr. R.K.B. Law College applied for starting a new 5 Years BBA.LL.B course in the institution to Bar Council of India and Dibrugarh University for approval in the year 2022. Preparations for the new course begin from the later half of the last year and in the month of May 2023, BCI conducted an inspection of the institution.

Policies of Good Practices

The institution has adopted several policies of good practices. These policies ensure a better environment on the principles of sustainable development. Some of such policies include: reutilizing the rough printed papers and again printing on the back blank side of such papers for casual activities that reduces wastage of papers; making cushion for office furniture from plastic wrappers of biscuits and other stuffs; recycling water and reducing the wastage of water in the

Later on June 13, 2023, experts from Dibrugarh University also visited the institution for inspection. On complying to all the necessary requirements for initiating the new course under the BCI and Dibrugarh University Rules and after adhering to all the required formalities, approval was provided by both BCI and the University. The institution has therefore opened up admissions to welcome new young students to the institution and for delivering young legal professionals to the nations' fraternity of legal professionals. Students after passing HS Final (Class XII) examination in any stream from recognized institutions will be now eligible to take admission in this institution for this course while previously only graduated students were eligible to take admission in the 3 year course. This course is expected to increase the level of competition among the students in the academic sphere and also with a larger number of students, the institution is expected to get even more strength for fulfilling its objectives.

washrooms, etc. The institution has also established the Eco-sense Club for ensuring environmental awareness and conducting activities that are necessary for protecting the environment. It has also declared its campus as Tobacco-Free Campus and has also adopted policies like No-Vehicle Day. The students are also advised to donate blood and free blood donation camps and health check-up camps are also organized at regular intervals. Such activities have also contributed to several health benefits for not only the members of the institution but also for the entire society as well. In addition, the Governing Body of the institution has also allowed the Senior Citizens to use its campus on every Sundays for organizing their meetings and other engagements.

Infrastructure

Administrative Block

The administration of the College is run from the wooden bungalow which was originally residential building of Dr. Rohini Kanta Barua.

The bungalow is one of the heritage building of the Dibrugarh town. The administrative building covers the Principal's office, Vice-Principal's office, Teachers' Common Room, College Office, Internal Quality Assurance Cell and Legal Aid Cell.

Academic Block

The Academic Block of the College is a two storied building which covers three class rooms, Library of the College, Moot Court Hall and Auditorium of the College.

Auditorium

The Auditorium of the College was inaugurated on 11th May, 2013 by then Minister of DONER Sri Panban Singh Gatowar , in presence of Sri Nogen saikia, Ex-Chair Person of Axom Sahitya Sabha, District Judge, Dibrugarh, Sri Rumi Phukan, Vice Chancellor of Dibrugarh University and Sri Kandarpa Kumar Deka. The College has a well equipped auditorium with seating capacity of over 200 people which is a regular venue for conference, workshop, seminar etc. The auditorium is also used by the students to exhibit their talents during cultural programmes of the college. In the Auditorium, the College organizes various seminars, workshop, awareness programme etc from time to time.

Library with internet facility

The college library is equipped with computer along with internet facilities and photocopy service to the members of the library. It follows open access system and using KOHA software. Book Lending Service has been offered to all library users. Library is administered by the Librarian. Library Development Committee looks into proper administration and development of the college library.

Moot Court Hall

Dr. R.K.B. Law College, provide an exclusive infrastructure for moot court class of the students so that they can acquire excellent practical knowledge.

Legal Aid Cell

The Legal Aid Cell of Dr. R.K.B Law College has been established in the college premises to extend free legal advice and assistance to the under privileged sections in the society. The students of Dr. R.K.B Law College, with the assistance of the faculty and practicing lawyers provide free legal advice to the needy people. The Cell also organizes various Legal-Aid and Awareness camps in the rural areas in the vicinity of Dibrugarh District.

IQAC

With the object augment the quality affirmation practices and to safeguard the exhaustive excellence and academic merit, Dr. Rohini Kanta Barua Law College initiated the establishment of IQAC in the institution. The functions of internal quality assurance cell are: Development and Application of quality benchmarks/parameters for the various academic and administrative activities of the college; Arrangement for feedback responses from students, parents and other stakeholders on quality related processes; Organization of intra and inter institutional workshops, seminars and quality related themes and promotion of quality circles; etc.

Smart Classroom

The institution also has smart classroom facilities. It provides for access to digital board, internet facilities, video conferencing facilities, better audio gadgets, etc. that makes learning interesting and enhances the scope of knowledge by allowing distant experts to interact with the students. Till date a number of classes and seminars have been conducted with the help of these facilities.

Staff of Dr. R.K.B. Law College

Teaching Staff

Dr. Gautomi Dutta Borah
Principal

Mrs. Manalisa Medhi
Assistant Professor

Dr. Manomita Paul
Assistant Professor

Mrs. Shilpi Gupta
Assistant Professor

Sri Sudeb Ch. Goswami
Visiting Faculty

Sri Satya Brata Sarma
Part-Time Faculty (Vice Principal)

Sr. R.K. Agarwalla
Part-Time Faculty

Sri Ajit Borgohain
Part-Time Faculty

Dr. Bijeta Chetry
Assistant Professor

Mrs. Ritimoni Sarma
Assistant Professor

Mr. Jayanta Boruah
Assistant Professor

Mrs. Sangita Saikia
Librarian

Mr. Srimanta Bordoloi
Visiting Faculty

Dr. Mahesh Jain
Visiting Faculty

Non-Teaching Staff

Ranjit Chakraborty
Accountant

Bitashree Gogoi
Office Assistant

Jyotshna Phukan Dutta
Library Assistant

Monikanta Hatimuria
Peon

Ramdeo Rai
Security In-charge

Governing Body

President
Dr. Prakash Barooah,
Retd. Joint Director,
Dept. of Health,
Govt. of Meghalaya

Secretary
Dr. Gautomi Dutta Borah,
Principal,
Dr. R.K.B. Law College

Member
Prof. (Dr.) L.R. Saikia,
Dibrugarh University
Nominee

Member
Prof. (Dr.) Deb Kr. Chakraborty
Dibrugarh University
Nominee

Member
Sir Rajkumar Agarwalla
Teachers' Representative

Member
Dr. Manomita Paul
Teachers' Representative

Member
Dr. Rajee Konwar
Retd. Principal
Kanoi College

Member
Sri Rituparna Barua,
Chairman, Tourism
Development Corpora-
tion, Govt. of Assam

Member
Dr. Uttara Dowerah
Donor's Nominee

Member
Dr. Ramananda Das
Guardians' Representa-
tive

Member
A/F
State Government Official

Ex-Officio Member
Sri Satya Brata Sarma
Vice Principal

